

Study the Factors Affecting the Choice of Accommodation for New Students: Case in Da Nang City, Vietnam

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Abstract—The objective of this study was to evaluate the factors affecting the choice of accommodation for new students at universities and colleges in Da Nang City, Vietnam. The research results show that there are 6 factors influencing the choice of accommodation: (1) Location; (2) Facilities; (3) quality of service; (4) Living environment; (5) security and (6) Price. Based on the results of the study, the author has proposed some suggestions to help first-year students choose the right accommodation to ensure their study.

Keywords— Accommodation, new students, Da Nang.

I. INTRODUCTION

"Becoming a student" - Wishing most students in high school, even smaller. That is the goal, the destination they are determined to achieve. University is the shortest path, bringing success and knowledge to students. When you study at university students will be more professional, easier to find a stable job. Also experience the student life, because it is the best time for us to explore the different aspects of this life.

Da Nang city is famous for its many unique bridges, ranked among the top cities worth living in Vietnam. There are many schools such as: Universities, Colleges, Intermediate and Continuing Education are professionally trained. That is why students focus primarily on this city.

But the dormitories at school only meet a small proportion of students. So most freshmen are struggling to find accommodation. The accommodation is limited, so students often have to rent at high prices, rent far away, sometimes have to accept poor quality. Most students come from different provinces, the amount Parents also have limits so finding a quality place to live is very difficult. Away from home, they have to worry about all their problems in life, from eating, living to learning, traveling. Families, schools, organizations, and local governments are usually only interested in learning but are rarely interested in improving the quality of student life, particularly in the area of student accommodation. Housing is the first condition for the development of human resources - a very important factor, which affects the academic results of students. The study of this topic aims at contributing to the school's perception of student accommodation. These things are of great significance in motivating students to study better, to improve the quality of education.

II. BACKGROUND STUDIES

There are many researches related to the choice of accommodation of students in countries around the world and Vietnam. That shows a lot of interest in this research. Most of these studies share a common perception that housing factors are most influential in the choice of housing, studies by Liu, Mingyang and He, Ritong (2013) show positive relationships. The location of residence influences the student's choice of accommodation, or Oyetunji Abiodun Kolawolea, Abidoye Rotimi Boluwatifeb (2016), suggests that accommodation near the campus is an important factor influencing student choice. Choosing accommodation or as Judith Thomsen (2007) points out the location factors that affect student satisfaction and choice of accommodation. In addition to location factors, housing facilities were referred to by researchers as a determinant of housing choice. Judith Thomsen (2007) said that students will prefer to choose a place with beautiful architecture and furniture, comfortable and appropriate. Nurul Ulyani Mohd Najib, Nor Aini Yusof, and Zulkifli Osman (2011) argue that the infrastructure factor will determine the choice of accommodation when accommodation costs are the same. Quality of service is one of the factors mentioned in most studies related to the choice of accommodation in general and the accommodation of students in particular. Hoang Thi Dieu Thuy (2011) suggested that the service quality is better the higher the choice behavior. Liu, Mingyang and He, Ritong (2013) accommodation services will be a decisive factor in the choice of accommodation. There are a lot of researches on living environment (relatives, friends, host family relationship, etc.) as Hoang Phuong Lien (2015) mentions new living environment which causes most students to leave. Away from home and independent with a life with many new things around.

In developing countries in general and in Vietnam in particular, most of the high-concentration areas are often cluttered in terms of security and order. Most of the rented student hostel is cheap because students usually do not have much money. The issue of security and order has been Hoang Phuong Lien (2015); Hoang Thi Dieu Thuy (2011) and many other authors in Vietnam mentioned in their research.

Finally, it is the price factor that can be considered as the most influential factor in the choice of accommodation. There are many authors referring to this element as Oyetunji

Abiodun Kolawolea, Abidoeye Rotimi Boluwatifeb (2016); Judith Thomsen (2007); Hoang Phuong Lien (2015) ... Most of the students studying in Danang are from the poorer provinces of central Vietnam. These students do not dare to choose accommodations that are too expensive beyond their own ability to pay

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Objectives of the Study

In recent years, the number of freshmen in Da Nang has been increasing. Therefore, the need for accommodation, accommodation is a very necessary issue. There are many adolescents who are far from home so they have to find suitable accommodation, which may be a dormitory, a relative's house ... but still not meet the demand for accommodation for the number. The student population is so large. Therefore, the article will address two main objectives. First, students rely on the factors that influence the choice of a stable, safe place. This is the first and hardest problem that students face. Secondly, through the results of our research, we offer solutions that make the choice of accommodation for first-year undergraduate students in Da Nang more effective and recommendations for the stakeholders to help students can sheltered accommodation during the first academic year.

3.2 Survey Method

Surveyed subjects: About 500 first-year students from universities and colleges in Ho Chi Minh City. Danang. Including about 10 universities, colleges such as Da Nang University, Duy Tan University, East Asia University, Da Nang Architecture University ... With the period from 1 to 2018 to 2018

3.3 Research Model

From the previous studies and the model that was developed in those studies, the author gives the model for the study as follows:

Fig. 1. Suggested research model

Through the above model, we can generalize the research concepts as follows:

+ Location is one of the most important factors in the search for a student's residence, although this issue is receiving attention from many sides (schools,), but the social reality does not meet the needs of students. In that the

accommodation is convenient for moving to the learning place. That is an important issue that needs attention and attention. From there, we have the right balance between learning as well as location for students.

Facilities are understood to be the factors associated with student accommodation such as access roads, light of rented rooms, the most essential facilities associated with the job. Accommodation: fan, drawer, cabinet, ... Besides, the quality of the room is new or old

Quality of service: The majority of student accommodation has poor and inadequate quality of services such as: hygienic accommodation, internet speed, food court, etc. cannot guarantee a place to study. Vacation, best rest for students. Therefore, their quality of living is not stable.

Living environment is one of the aspects worth mentioning. Because in community relationships, most students have close relationships with roommates, but have a normal relationship with the hostess, the local people, and the place they live. In addition, the character of the hostess also affects the rent of rooms, or neighbors around the house that affect the choice of accommodation or not.

Security: There are many factors that affect the choice of accommodation of students, but the elements of security and order are one of the important factors in the criteria for accommodation of students. Expressed through: (security gate, fence, ...), the security and order contacts if the evils occur quickly and in time and accommodation with fire prevention and treatment Fire.

Price is the factor that affects the choice of accommodation. This is reflected in the following criteria: room rental rates, costs incurred (water, electricity, gas, ..), the host reported increase room rates, or, the cost of travel to the place Study is suitable,

Each factor influences more or less on the decision to choose a place to live. It is the choice of location, material, service quality, living environment, security and order, price. It can be said that housing is not only a place of residence, but also a harmony between learning as well as the relationship in society. These factors, which are factors that affect the choice of accommodation for freshman.

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS

There are 500 votes, 450 votes (90%), 45 votes invalid. Thus, the final sample size was 405, of which 216 males and 189 females.

TABLE 1. Results of reliability analysis of variable groups by Cronbach'Alpha coefficient

No	Group variables	Number of observation variables	Cronbach's Alpha
1	Location	3	0.804
2	Facilities	4	0.810
3	Quality of service	4	0.829
4	Living environment	3	0.756
5	Security	3	0.762
6	Price	4	0.754
7	Decision to choose	4	0.849

Source: Author synthesis

Based on the Cronbach Alpha coefficient analysis, seven components of the measure of student impact factor and

dependency ratio were found to have a reliability greater than 0.6. This shows that the scale is statistically significant and the reliability coefficient is required. Should be further included in the EFA discovery factor analysis.

Analyzing the EFA Discovery Factor

After measuring the reliability of the scale with the Cronbach Alpha coefficient and removing the variables that do not guarantee reliability, further analysis of the EFA discovery factor will be performed. This is the technique used to extract the observed variables into one or several factors. The EFA exploratory factor analysis was used extensively in the study to evaluate the baseline scales.

Analysis of the EFA factor of independent variables

First, to check if the independent factors are relevant for inclusion in the EFA discovery factor analysis, we conduct Bartlett's test and the KMO coefficient:

TABLE 2. KMO Coefficients and Bartlett's Test of Independent Factors

Hệ số KMO		0.872
Kiểm định Bartlett's	Approx. Chi-Square	2036.853
	Df	353
	Sig.	0.000

Source: Author synthesis

Based on Table 2, the KMO value is $0.872 > 0.5$ and the Bartlett's Sig value of $0.000 < 0.05$ indicates that the variables are correlated, so the model is suitable for inclusion in exploratory factor analysis.

The extraction method in factor analysis requires that extracts of Eigenvalue be greater than 1 to be retained in the analytical model. The six extracted factors have an Eigenvalue value greater than 1 and the stoppage when extracting the factors at factor 6 has an Eigenvalue of $1.010 > 1$. The total deviation of the six factors equals $70.789\% > 50\%$ of this. The ability to use these six factors explains the 70.789% variability of the observed variables.

Factor analysis reveals EFA factor satisfaction

The results of the EFA factor analysis with KMO are $0.800 > 0.5$ and Bartlett's test has a sig value of $0.000 < 0.05$, so it is possible to confirm the data for factor analysis. (Table 3)

TABLE 3. KMO Coefficients and Bartlett's Test of Choice Factors

Hệ số KMO		0.800
Kiểm định Bartlett's	Approx. Chi-Square	537.686
	Df	156
	Sig.	0.000

Source: Author synthesis

The analysis extracted from the 4 variables evaluates the experiment as a major factor having an Eigenvalue of 2.753 and a total deviation of $68.836\% > 50\%$.

TABLE 4. Total variance of the factor of choice

STT	Eigenvalues			Squared load factor		
	Total	% variance	% cumulative error	Total	% variance	% cumulative error
1	2.753	68.836	68.836	2.753	68.836	68.836
2	.527	13.169	82.005			
3	.432	10.807	92.812			
4	.288	7.188	100.000			

Source: Author synthesis

Analysis of regression models

After extracting the elements from the exploratory factor analysis, we conduct a regression analysis to determine the factors affecting the choice of first-year residence. Regression analysis will be conducted with 6 independent factors: Location, facilities, quality of service, living environment, security and order and price.

The value of each factor used to run the regression is the mean of the observed variables of that factor.

The multivariable linear regression of this study has the form:

Overall regression function:

$$SULC = \beta_0 + \beta_1DIDI + \beta_2CSVC + \beta_3CLDV + \beta_4MTSO + \beta_5ANTT + \beta_6GICA + U_i$$

Sample regression:

$$SULC = \beta_0 + \beta_1DIDI + \beta_2CSVC + \beta_3CLDV + \beta_4MTSO + \beta_5ANTT + \beta_6GICA + e_i$$

Inside:

SULC: Student accommodation choice

DIDI: Location

CSVC: Facilities

CLDV: Quality of service

MTSO: Living environment

ANTT: Security

GICA: Price

The regression model finds the independent factors that influence the dependent variable. At the same time, the model also describes how the impact can be predicted by the factor. Conduct regression with new variables and give the following results:

TABLE 5. Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.697 ^a	.669	.620	.36453	2.007

a. Predictors: (Constant), DIDIs, CSVCs, CLDVs, MTSOs, ANTTs, GICAs
b. Dependent Variable: SULCs

TABLE 6. ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	38.508	5	6.374	41.044	.000 ^a
	Residual	51.491	306	.250		
	Total	90.289	317	6.374		

a. Predictors: (Constant), DIDIs, CSVCs, CLDVs, MTSOs, ANTTs, GICAs
b. Dependent Variable: SULCs

TABLE 7. Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.5983	.146		3.893	.000
DIDIs	.068	.039	.132	3.051	.001
CSVCs	.215	.047	.187	3.279	.002
CLDVs	.179	.038	.242	5.178	.001
MTSOs	.142	.041	.168	3.098	.000
ANTTs	.209	.051	.197	3.498	.000
GICAs	.148	.056	.201	4.976	.000

a. Dependent Variable: SULCs

Source: Author synthesis

The determined coefficient is 0.620; Durbin-Watson statistics are 2007 and statisticians $F = 41.044$ (Sig. = 0.000).

Thus the model exists and with $d = 2,007 \approx 2,0$, it can be concluded that the model does not exist negative or positive self-correlation phenomena.

With this result, we compute $b_j = c_j$ with $j > 0$ and $b_0 = c_0 / (1-r)$, so the estimation model will be:

$$SULC * = 0.132DIDI * + 0.187CSVC * + 0.242CLDV * + 0.168MTSO * + 0.197ANTT + 0.201GICA$$

Based on the ANOVA table with Sig value = 0.000 < 0.05, reject the null hypothesis, assuming H1 hypothesis. That is, the pattern exists. In other words, with a 5% significance level, it can be concluded that the choice of student accommodation is influenced by at least one of the six factors (location, facilities, quality of service, environment living, security and Price).

V. CONCLUSION

From the above analysis, we show the direction of the factors affecting the residence for the first student in the Da nang city

First, for the Da Nang City Committee

- Create conditions for universities to build dormitories, businesses that want to build rental homes. Get good locations, cool, quiet, away from the factories. Capital support as well as the construction of student dormitories. Encourage businesses in Da Nang City to invest in building low-cost homestay for students.
- Control the search pages for students on social housing in the city of Da Nang, to avoid the case of students brokered, cheated money.

Second, For Universities, Colleges

- The school must take the initiative of first-year students to know the specific school schedule in which to choose suitable accommodation for travel. Building dormitories on campus for students.
- Links to families who have been renting a room near the facility where the first year student is studying, to help make it easier for you to travel, as well as rent accommodation.
- The school built dormitory: full of electrical equipment, large bathroom, computer, washing machine, cooking place for students. There is a cafeteria, dining room, dormitory, for students to eat, as well as daily necessities.
- Habitat: There are green trees around, sport gymnasium, cool place ... Quiet, quiet accommodation for learning, away from crowded, noisy places as well as places. have factories, factories.
- Security and order: separate zones: male students, female students, gate guard 24/24, time limit: 23h, sheltered car park, safe Fire fighting equipment is located in each room.
- Price: Electricity Water tariff at the state prices, schools have policies to support, reasonable prices, not too high compared with prices outside.

Third, For Students

- Find ways to rent a room, Find out more information related to: price, location, security, .. through the student office or through friends or acquaintances, ... To do Clear contracts on

how much, such as how much to pay, how much to pay for a particular lease, how long to rent, etc.

- The contract must be split into two copies, one for each party. Students can refer to the deposit form, contract online and may ask the landlord to provide a copy of their ID card and household registration booklet. If the landlord fails to comply with the contract, hold the deposit, the student holds the papers by the street quarter, neighborhood, police intervention.

Fourth, Other Parties

- About accommodation, student accommodation. We only need to type the room, the name of the area when the list is not read all. However, 95% of the online news is from the broker posted so we have to know selectively. First, you should pay attention to the post time. Second, to determine the middleman or landlord, you just search the contact phone number on Google, if you are an intermediary then you will see all kinds of information related to the sdt such as enrollment, sales home, land sale
- Broker is also an option, but if the fee of 30, 40 or 50% of the first month, or you pay the fee tomorrow to check in, pay the fee before the notice will be you You need to be careful with ads that are attractive but not obvious on renting rooms, motels, because it may be through brokers, " trigger "home. In my experience, new students should not find a hostel online.

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